

NFDI4Chem, Chemistry Consortium in the NFDI

Activity Report

Open project plan continuously updated on portal

TA1 - Management

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Contributing partner(s): all partners

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Executive Summary

The work plan as laid out in the proposal is being integrated in a detailed work plan with a timeline, which is accessible to all partners of the NFDI4Chem. Regular reporting and monitoring of various indicators will ensure control of the project and provoke changes to the plan, if necessary.

Project objectives

With this activity, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) This activity contributes to all objectives in the project as it ensures timely completion of the deliverables in all Task Areas.

Detailed report on the deliverable

All deliverables as laid out in the proposal have been transferred to OpenProject, an online project management tool, which is accessible to all members of the NFDI4Chem Project. The OpenProject software allows to track deliverables and their due date and hence facilitates to identify deliverables that run the risk of being delayed. Once a deliverable is finished, the deliverable is being set to 'completed' in the OpenProject software and a deliverable report with further details is written.

The reports, which contain an executive summary and description of completed deliverables, are published on Zenodo as activity reports and referenced on the NFDI4Chem portal > About Us > Project Updates. Reports containing confidential information will not be published.

Each quarter, every task area summarises its progress in short in so-called flash reports. It contains information on finished deliverables, meetings, completion of sub-tasks as well as past and upcoming events. A compilation of the flash reports is circulated among all project partners and also published on the NFDI4Chem portal > About Us > Project Updates.

Additionally, regular meetings of the steering committee, the project managers and within the task areas (see Deliverable 1.2.1) ensure constant monitoring and, if necessary, adjustment of the roadmap and responsibilities.

References

URL of the NFDI4Chem portal subpage with reference to activity and flash reports:

<https://www.nfdi4chem.de/index.php/project-updates/>